

Extraction and Spectrophotometric Determination of Copper(II) with Isonitrosothiocamphor (HINTC)

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A spectrophotometric method based on the extraction of Cu(II) with isonitrosothiocamphor in chloroform and measurement of the colour in the organic phase at 430 nm is described. Beer's law is obeyed in the range 0.1 to 5.0 μg Cu per ml. The average of ten determinations with 20 μg Cu in 10 ml aqueous solution is 19.4 μg which varies between 18.3 and 20.5 μg at 95% confidence limit. 0.1 μg Cu in 1 ml solution gives an absorbance of 0.01.

ISONITROSOTHIOCAMPHOR (HINTC) reacts with transition metal ions forming coloured complexes which are extractable in organic solvents. Its application as an indicator in acidimetry and alkalimetry¹ and as a gravimetric reagent² for the determination of cobalt in the presence of nickel has been reported. However, the use of this reagent for the extraction and spectrophotometric determination of copper has not been reported in the literature. The present paper reports a systematic study on the extraction and spectrophotometric determination of copper with HINTC.

Experimental

A Carl-Zeiss VSU-2P spectrophotometer was used for absorbance measurements. Radioactivity and pH were measured as described earlier³.

All chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Stock solution of copper was prepared and analysed by standard method⁴. Solutions for interference study were obtained by dissolving appropriate salts in water to give 10 mg of the element per ml and they were standardised by standard methods. HINTC was synthesised by literature procedure¹. Radioisotopes, ¹³⁷Cs, ⁵¹Cr, ⁴⁵Ca, ⁵⁴Mn, ¹⁴⁴Ce, ¹²⁴Sb, ⁶⁵Zn, ⁷⁵Se, ⁵⁹Fe, ¹¹⁵Cd, ²⁰⁴Tl, ⁶⁰Co and ²⁰³Hg were procured from the Isotope Division, Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Trombay, Bombay.

Procedure for extraction and spectrophotometric determination of copper :

2 ml 0.04 M sodium acetate solution and 1 ml 6% ethanolic solution of isonitrosothiocamphor were added to a solution containing 1 mg copper. The mixture was made upto 10 ml and equilibrated for 1 min with an equal volume of an organic solvent. The two phases were allowed to separate and copper in each phase was determined by the diethyldithiocarbamate method⁵. The pH of the equilibrated aqueous phase was measured. In the study of the interference by other ions, the ion of interest was

added before adding the reagent. Radioactive tracers, whenever available, were used to follow the extraction of other ions. The values for the separation factor (S) defined as :

$$S = \frac{\text{Distribution ratio of copper}}{\text{Distribution ratio of element of interest}}$$

was calculated.

For spectrophotometric determination, 4 ml solution containing 1 to 50 μg copper was mixed with 2 ml 0.4 M sodium acetate and 0.5 ml 0.62% HINTC in alcohol. The pH of the mixture was adjusted to ~ 4 with dilute solution of NaOH or HCl. 2 ml buffer solution of sodium acetate and HCl of pH 4 was added. The mixture was made up to 10 ml and equilibrated for 1 minute with 10 ml chloroform. The chloroform layer was collected in a 10 ml measuring flask and made up to the mark with chloroform, if required. The absorbance of the solution was measured at 430 nm using a reagent blank. The amount of copper present was determined from a calibration curve.

Procedure for the determination of Cu in steel :

Steel sample (0.1-0.2 g) was dissolved in 10 ml HCl (3 : 2) by boiling on a hot plate. 2 ml conc. HNO₃ was added and the mixture was boiled. The solution was evaporated to dryness to remove oxides of nitrogen. The residue was dissolved in 10 ml 6.5 N HCl and filtered and the volume was made upto 25 ml with 6.5 N HCl. An aliquot of the acid solution was equilibrated with diisopropyl ether to extract Fe(III)⁶. The aqueous acid phase was evaporated to dryness. The residue was treated with 5 ml water and the solution was analysed for Cu as described above.

Results and Discussion

The results of extraction studies show that copper can be quantitatively extracted in benzene from an aqueous alcoholic solution containing HINTC at

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pH 3-7. Below and above this pH range, the extraction of copper decreases. The extraction is rapid and quantitative when HINTC and metal are in the ratio of 10 : 1 or more.

The values for the extraction coefficient of copper give the following order for the organic solvents used :

benzene	~	chloroform	~	toluene	~	butanol
E=>1000	>	>1000	>	>1000	>	>1000
		~carbon tetrachloride	>			
			>	1000		
ether	>	nitromethane	>	nitrobenzene	>	
675		550		450		
ethyl acetate	>	chlorobenzene	>			
125		90				
methyl isobutyl ketone	>	methyl ethyl ketone.				
47		20				

The colour in chloroform is stable for a longer period than in benzene and so the former is used in the spectrophotometric determination of copper.

Neutral salts such as chlorides of lithium, sodium and potassium do not have significant effect on the extraction coefficient of copper. The extraction of copper is 99.9% in the presence of each of 100 mg of sulphate, sulphite, persulphate, nitrate, chloride, bromide, iodide, chlorate, phosphate, tartrate and acetate. Between 99.0 and 99.8% copper can be extracted in the presence of 100 mg each of citrate, iodate, urea, bromate, fluoride and thiocyanate. The extraction is 95.9% in the presence of 100 mg pyrophosphate. Sulphide and thiosulphate give precipitate. Cyanide, nitrite, oxalate, thiourea and EDTA interfere seriously. Interference due to these ions can be removed by boiling the mixture with HNO₃ before subjecting the solution to extraction.

Separation factors given in Table 1 indicate that copper can be efficiently separated from a number of elements. Co(II) is extracted along with copper in benzene under the experimental conditions used.

Spectrophotometric determination :

The absorption spectrum (Fig. 1) of Cu-HINTC in chloroform shows a maximum at 430 nm. The

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of HINTC (●—●), and Cu-HINTC (○—○) in chloroform. Conc. of Cu=7.85 × 10⁻⁵ and conc. of HINTC=78.75 × 10⁻⁶

absorption measurements are taken at this wavelength using a reagent blank. The plot of absorbance against concentration of copper gives a straight line in the range 0.1 to 5 μg per ml indicating that Beer's law is obeyed. The molar absorptivity of the coloured species, calculated on the basis of total metal taken, is 5559 l.mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹ at 430 nm. The absorbance of the solution does not show any change upto 90 min.

The variation of the reagent concentration from 0.03 to 0.12% does not have significant effect on the colour developed with 20 μg copper. 0.5 ml of 0.62% reagent in alcohol is used for the estimation of 1 to 50 μg copper in 10 ml solution. However, in the presence of 10 mg of other ions which interact with HINTC, it is necessary to use 1.24% solution of HINTC.

The following ions, when present in the amounts indicated below, do not interfere in the spectrophotometric determination of 20 μg copper. 10 mg each of calcium(II), barium(II), strontium(II), zinc(II), tungsten(VI) and selenium(IV); 5 mg of chromium(III); 1 mg each of molybdenum(VI), manganese(II), arsenic(III), cadmium(II), mercury(II), aluminium(III), iridium(III), rhodium(III); 100 μg each of nickel(II), bismuth(III), antimony(III), ruthenium(III), osmium(VIII); 10 μg each of silver(I), vanadium(V), gold(III), palladium(II), cobalt(II), tin(IV), platinum(IV). 10 mg magnesium do not interfere when 1.24% HINTC is used.

100 mg each of urea, acetate, chloride, sulphate; 50 mg of tartrate; 25 mg each of phosphate, pyrophosphate; 10 mg each of chloride, bromide, fluoride, bromate, nitrate, persulphate, thiocyanate and 1 mg each of thiourea, iodide, iodate do not have significant effect on the development of colour and extraction.

In the presence of sulphide, copper gives precipitate. Sulphide, nitrite, thiosulphate, citrate,

TABLE 1—SEPARATION FACTORS FOR DIFFERENT IONS IN THE EXTRACTION OF Cu-HINTC COMPOUND INTO BENZENE AT pH 4

Total copper taken :	1 mg
Aqueous phase :	10 ml
Organic phase :	10 ml benzene
Separation factor greater than	Ions
10 ⁷	Ca(II)
10 ⁶	Cr(III), Cs(I), Mn(II)
10 ⁵	Ce(III), Sb(III), Zn(II), Se(IV), Fe(III)*, Ni(II), Cd(II)
10 ⁴	Tl(I)
10 ³	Co(II)
3.3	Hg(II)

* in the presence of tartrate.

oxalate, cyanide and EDTA interfere by hindering the extraction of copper in chloroform. Interference due to these reagents can be removed by boiling the mixture with HNO_3 before the extraction.

Nature of the extracted species :

The composition of the extracted species has been determined by Job's method of continuous variation and the mole-ratio method.

Plot of absorbance against mole-ratio of HINTC : Cu reveals breaks corresponding to the mole-ratios 2 and 4. Job's continuous variation method shows maximum at 0.20 and 0.33 mole fraction of copper, indicating that the coloured complexes extracted into chloroform are formed by the reaction of Cu and HINTC in the ratios of 1 : 2 and 1 : 4. This supports the composition of the extracted complexes as $\text{Cu}(\text{INTC})_2$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{INTC})_4 \cdot 2\text{HINTC}$.

Precision, accuracy and sensitivity :

The precision and accuracy of the proposed method were tested by analysing solutions containing known amounts of copper. The average of 10 determinations with 20 μg copper in 10 ml solution is 19.4 μg . Standard deviation is 0.73 μg . 0.1 μg Cu in 1 ml solution gives an absorbance of 0.01.

Results of analysis of the steel sample are in good agreement with those reported in the certificate

issued by the U. S. National Bureau of Standard as shown in Table 2.

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF COPPER IN STEEL
Percentage of copper

Found	Reported
0.072	0.072
0.070	

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